

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COST AND RETURNS AMONG BENEFICIARY AND NON- BENEFICIARY COTTON FARMERS USING UPPER WARDHA DAM IRRIGATION IN AMRAVATI DISTRICT.

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Abstract:

The construction of dams plays a crucial role in enhancing irrigation systems, which is particularly beneficial for agricultural productivity. This study examines "Comparative analysis of cost and returns among beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers using Upper Wardha Dam Irrigation", specifically focusing on cotton farmers. The research compares the cost and returns of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers in three tehsils: Morshi, Twisa and Dhamangaon Railway. Data were collected from 48 farmers (24 beneficiary and 24 non-beneficiary) during the year 2023-24. The study explores the cost and returns of cotton production, Results show that beneficiary farmers, who have access to dam water for irrigation, exhibit significantly higher crop yields compared to non-beneficiaries. The output-input ratio at cost 'C₃' for beneficiary farmers was 1.40, while for non-beneficiaries, it was 1.08, indicating higher profitability among the former.

Keywords: Beneficiary, Non-beneficiary, Productivity, Input-Output ratio, Cotton.

Introduction:

The Upper Wardha Dam, located in the Amravati district of Maharashtra, is a key infrastructural project aimed at improving irrigation and water management in the region. The dam is constructed on the Wardha River, a major tributary of the Godavari River, and serves as a critical water source for agricultural activities in the surrounding areas. It was designed to provide year-round irrigation, helping farmers in the region overcome challenges related to water scarcity, particularly during dry spells and erratic rainfall patterns.

The dam's primary objective is to enhance water availability for irrigation, thereby increasing agricultural productivity and stabilizing farmers' incomes. With the increased irrigation potential, the Upper Wardha Dam has enabled the cultivation of various crops, including cotton, soybean, and other cash crops, which are essential to the region's economy. The dam also plays a role in flood control and improving the overall water supply for domestic and industrial use in the region.

By providing a consistent and reliable water supply, the Upper Wardha Dam has the potential to improve both the productivity and profitability of farmers, particularly those in areas that previously faced unreliable water availability. Despite its benefits, challenges such as equitable water distribution and the costs associated with dam maintenance remain areas of concern. This research aims to assess the impact of the Upper Wardha Dam on the agricultural income of farmers, focusing on both beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers.

Materials and Methods:

The standard cost concepts i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ were used in present analysis.

Cost A₁: All variable cost excluding family labour cost and including depreciation.

- 1) Value of Hired human labour (HL)
- 2) Value of hired and owned bullock labour (BL)
- 3) Value of hired and owned machine labour (ML)
- 4) Value of seeds
- 5) Value of insecticides and pesticides
- 6) Value of manure
- 7) Value of fertilizers
- 8) Irrigation charges
- 9) Depreciation on implements and farm building
- 10) Land revenue, cesses and other taxes
- 11) Interest on working capital
- 12) Miscellaneous expenses

Cost A₂: Cost A₁ + Rent paid for leased-in land

Cost B₁: Cost A₂ + interest value of owned fixed capital assets (excluding land)

Cost B₂: Cost B₁ + rental value of owned land and rent paid for leased in land.

Cost C₁: Cost B₁ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₂: Cost B₂ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₃: Cost C₂ + 10 per cent of Cost C₂ on account of managerial functions performed by farmers.

Gross and net returns**Gross returns**

Gross return of the farmers under the present study was estimated from returns obtained from sale of main produce.

Gross returns = Value of main produce + Value of by produce

Net returns

Net returns were computed at different costs i.e., Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by deducting respective costs from the gross returns.

Net income at cost A₁ = Gross return – cost A₁

Net income at cost A₂ = Gross return – cost A₂

Net income at cost B₁ = Gross return – cost B₁

Net income at cost B₂ = Gross return – cost B₂

Net income at cost C₁ = Gross return – cost C₁

Net income at cost C₂ = Gross return – cost C₂

Net income at cost C₃ = Gross return – cost C₃

Input- output ratio

It was calculated at cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by dividing gross income by respective cost.

Results and discussion:

The findings of the present study as well as relevant discussion have been presented under following heads.

Per hectare input utilization of Cotton.

Cotton is an important fiber crop grown by the farmers in study area. As revealed from Table 1 use of manure on beneficiary farm (1.08 tonnes) was slightly more than non-beneficiary farms (0.87 tonnes). Beneficiary farmers applied more quantity of fertilizers than the non-beneficiary farms. Use of hired human labour days on beneficiary farms (75.55 days) and non-beneficiary farmers (90.90.95 days). Use of family human male and female labour days on beneficiary farms (7.45 days) and non-beneficiary farmers (17.00 days). Use of seed on beneficiary farms was (2.57 kg/ha) and on non- beneficiary farms was 2.53 kg/ha) use of seed slightly more than non- beneficiary farms. Intergroup comparison of beneficiary and non- beneficiary farms also revealed the same trend.

Cost of cultivation of cotton for beneficiary farmers:

The share of each item to the total cost i.e., cost C₃ for cotton cultivation. The cost has determined on the basis of standard cost concept i.e., cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂, cost C₃, the different cost concepts have different utilities in research. Here and attempt has been made to estimate the figures of cost of cotton crop of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers in the study area and presented in table 2.

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton grown by the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers is presented in Table 2 that, in case of beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton crop for the sample as an overall level was Rs. 93479.79. The per ha. total

cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'C₃' ranges from Rs. 86418.96 in head reach, Rs. 88292.91 in mid reach and Rs. 98810.38 in tail reach respectively.

In case of beneficiary the per ha. cost of cultivation at overall level i.e., cost A₁ and cost A₂ was Rs. 57687.91 and Rs. 57687.91 respectively which was 61.71 per cent and 61.71 per cent of total cost i.e., cost C₃. The per ha. cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 52629.34 in head reach which was 60.90 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha cost of cultivation in mid reach i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 54265.95 which was 61.46 per cent of total cost i.e., cost C₃. The per ha. cost of cultivation in tail reach at cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 61923.39 which was 62.67 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' respectively.

The per ha. overall cost of beneficiary farmers cost B₁ and B₂ was Rs. 59235.05 (63.37) and Rs. 80949.81 (86.60) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in head reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 53939.24 (62.42) and Rs. 75290.01 (87.12) per cent. The per ha cost B₁ and B₂ in mid reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 55987.67 (63.41) and Rs. 76262.03 (86.37) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in tail reach beneficiary farmers was Rs. 63533.20 (64.30) and Rs. 84849.45 (85.87) per cent. In non-beneficiary group costs were lower as compared to beneficiary farmers as there was low level of input used.

In case of beneficiary farmers head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level share of hired human labour (male + female) to total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' accounted 18.36 per cent, 19.35 per cent, 23.70 per cent and 21.04 per cent respectively. This human labour used in various farm operations like ploughing, harrowing, sowing, hoeing, weeding, harvesting etc. Bullock labour accounted in case of head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level 2.29 per cent, 2.98 per cent, 3.23 per cent and 2.71 per cent respectively. Bullock labour used in the farm operation like ploughing, harrowing, hoeing and transport the farm produce from field to farmhouse. Machines used in farm operation like ploughing, harrowing etc. It included the share in total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' in case of head reach, mid reach, tail reach and at overall level were 1.54 per cent, 2.44 per cent, 2.27 per cent and 2.04 per cent respectively. At overall level the machinery cost was slightly more as compared to non-beneficiary farmers.

Cost of cultivation of cotton for non-beneficiary farmers:

The per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton grown by the non-beneficiary farmers is presented in Table 3, that, in case of non-beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton crop for the sample as an overall level was Rs. 89387.61. The per ha. total cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'C₃' ranges from Rs. 81120.36 in small size group, Rs. 84174.44 in medium size group and Rs. 92328.78 for large size group respectively. The per ha. cost in case of large size group of farmers was higher as input use level was higher.

In case of non-beneficiary, the per ha. cost of cultivation at overall level i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 57604.65 which was 64.44 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha. cost of cultivation i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was in small size group Rs. 53122.32 which was 65.49 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha cost of cultivation in medium size group i.e., cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 53854.53 which was 63.98 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃'. The per ha. Cost of cultivation in large size group is. cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' was Rs. 61169.92 which was 66.25 per cent of total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' respectively.

The per ha. overall cost of non-beneficiary farmers cost B₁ and B₂ was Rs. 59161.74 (66.19) and Rs. 75222.18 (84.15) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in small size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 54740.39 (67.48) and Rs. 69448.06 (85.61) per cent. The per ha cost B₁ and B₂ in medium size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 55472.60 (65.90) and Rs. 72552.27 (86.19) per cent. The per ha cost at B₁ and B₂ in large size group of non-beneficiary farmers was Rs. 62787.99 (68.00) and Rs. 79504.51 (86.11) per cent.

In case of non-beneficiary farmers small, medium, large and at overall level share of hired human labour (male + female) to total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' accounted 26.26 per cent, 26.86 per cent, 24.94 per cent and 24.86 per cent respectively. This human labour used in various farm

operations like ploughing, harrowing, sowing, hoeing, weeding, harvesting etc. Bullock labour accounted in case of small, medium, large and at overall level 4.76 per cent, 3.55 per cent, 6.78 per cent and 7.05 per cent respectively. Bullock labour used in the farm operation like ploughing, harrowing, hoeing and transport the farm produce from field to farmhouse. Machines used in farm operation like ploughing, harrowing etc. It included the share in total cost i.e., cost 'C₃' in case of small, medium, large and at overall level were 2.87 per cent, 2.18 per cent, 3.13 per cent and 2.56 per cent respectively.

1.4 Per hectare cost and returns of cotton for beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers:

The per hectare cost and returns from cotton is presented in table 4. It is revealed from the table 4, that at in case of beneficiary overall level average gross return worked out to Rs. 130801.03

The net return obtain at various costs were Rs. 73113.12 at cost A₁, Rs. 73113.12 at cost A₂, Rs. 71565.98 at cost B₁, Rs. 49851.22 at cost B₂, Rs. 67534.16 at cost C₁, Rs. 45819.40 at cost C₂, Rs. 37321.24 at cost C₃. The highest input-output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in head reach i.e., 1.49 and lowest input-output ratio at cost C₃ was recorded in tail reach i.e., 1.30. mid reach 1.38 input-output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.53. At overall level the input-output ratio at cost C₃ was 1.40.

In case of beneficiary farmers at head reach, mid reach, tail reach and overall level per hectare yield of main produce obtained from cotton 17.84 qt., 16.55 qt., 17.44 qt. and 17.90 qt. respectively, it was more as compared to non-beneficiary farmers which has seen in table 4. Yield increases 3-4 qt. more than the non-beneficiary farmers here impact of upper wardha dam is shown by providing irrigation to crop in dry spell.

In case of non-beneficiary farmers at overall level input output ratio at C₃ was 1.08 and for small, medium and large farmers it was 1.09, 1.22 and 1.09 respectively. It's shown that the beneficiary farmers were more profitable than non-beneficiary farmers the impact of gross returns was observed in case of beneficiary farmers due to irrigation from upper wardha dam in their field.

Conclusion:

It can be concluded that in case of beneficiary farmers higher per hectare input was used than non-beneficiary farmers. The beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton for the sample as an overall was Rs. 93479.79 i.e., cost 'C₃'. In case of non-beneficiary farmer per hectare cost of cultivation for cotton crop for the sample as an overall was Rs. 89387.61 i.e., cost 'C₃'. There was more per hectare cost of cultivation in case of beneficiary farmers than non-beneficiary farmers. The per hectare cost and returns from cotton in case of beneficiary at overall level average gross return worked out to the net returns obtained from cotton crop by beneficiary farmer are greater than non-beneficiary farmer. Input-output ratio was also greater than non-beneficiary that means the beneficiary farmers was more profitable as compared to non-beneficiary farmers.

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Table No:1 Impact on input utilization pattern of beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmer of cotton.

(Numbers/ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Head Reach	Mid Reach	Tail Reach	Overall	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	2	3		4	5	6	7	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	14.49	22.38	23.10	19.99	22.46	21.93	17.08	20.92
		Female	Days	41.11	40.62	60.95	55.56	69.02	70.26	71.23	70.03
		Total	Days	55.60	63.00	84.05	75.55	91.48	92.19	88.31	90.95
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	Days	2.96	5.18	3.02	1.46	4.15	4.81	6.45	6.45
		Owned	Days	1.03	0.31	3.04	3.72	1.66	0.82	2.00	2.00
		Total	Days	3.99	5.49	6.06	5.18	5.81	5.63	8.45	8.45
3	Machine charges	Hired	Hrs	2.33	3.59	3.54	3.15	3.88	3.05	4.81	3.80
4	seed		Kg.	2.57	2.52	2.63	2.57	2.49	2.56	2.54	2.53
5	Manures		Tonnes	1.12	1.00	1.12	1.08	0.77	0.55	1.50	0.87
6	Fertilizers	N kg/ha	Kg.	54.30	41.20	35.10	43.53	28.10	42.10	30.10	44.71
		P kg/ha	Kg.	81.45	61.80	52.65	65.30	28.10	30.08	26.10	28.61
		K kg/ha	Kg.	81.45	61.80	52.65	65.30	28.10	30.08	26.10	28.61
		Total	Kg.	217.20	164.80	140.40	174.13	84.30	102.26	82.30	101.93
7	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	6.88	8.25	10.00	8.37	9.84	9.55	7.14	9.06
		Female	Days	5.22	7.28	9.00	7.45	7.97	6.16	10.54	17.00
		Total	Days	12.10	15.53	19.00	15.82	17.81	15.71	17.68	26.06

Table No: 2 Cost of cultivation of cotton of beneficiary farmers.

(RS. /ha)

Particulars			Head Reach		Mid Reach		Tail Reach		Overall	
Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	4144.14	5.27	6445.44	8.03	6432.43	7.16	5742.33	6.76
		Female	10277.50	13.08	9085.07	11.32	14855.34	16.54	12137.08	14.28
		Total	14421.64	18.36	15530.51	19.35	21287.77	23.70	17879.41	21.04
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	2119.00	1.65	3424.19	2.80	2010.41	1.57	1058.92	0.81
		Owned	826.44	0.64	216.94	0.18	2135.02	1.66	2489.68	1.90
		Total	2945.45	2.29	3641.13	2.98	4145.44	3.23	3548.61	2.71
3	Machine charges	Hired	1328.10	1.54	2154.00	2.44	2244.50	2.27	1933.53	2.07
4	Seed	Kg/ha	2210.20	2.56	2167.20	2.45	2261.80	2.29	2211.31	2.37
5	Manures	Tonnes	2912.00	3.37	1600.00	1.81	2912.00	2.95	2592.00	2.77
6	Fertilizers	Nkg/ha	708.07	0.82	537.25	0.61	457.70	0.46	567.63	0.61
		P kg/ha	3685.61	4.26	2796.45	3.17	2382.41	2.41	2954.83	3.16
		K kg/ha	1629.00	1.89	1236.00	1.40	1053.00	1.07	1306.00	1.40
		Total	6022.68	6.97	4569.70	5.18	3893.12	3.94	4828.46	5.17
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)	661.16	0.77	920.10	1.04	1014.67	1.03	865.31	0.93
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)	644.76	0.75	1026.80	1.16	1092.66	1.11	921.41	0.99
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)	3034.00	3.51	4153.73	4.70	4119.13	4.17	3769.03	4.03
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)	443.96	0.51	660.02	0.75	751.83	0.76	618.51	0.66
11	Harvesting	(Rs.)	14272.00	16.51	13240.00	15.00	13952.00	14.12	14320.00	15.32
12	Working Capital	(Rs.)	48895.95	56.58	49663.18	56.25	57674.91	58.37	53487.57	57.22

13	Interest on working Capital	(Rs.)	3059.06	3.54	3100.53	3.51	3460.49	3.50	3209.25	3.43
14	Depreciation	(Rs.)	603.31	0.70	1413.92	1.60	700.00	0.71	905.67	0.97
15	Land Revenue	(Rs.)	71.02	0.08	88.31	0.10	87.98	0.09	85.41	0.09
16	COST "A₁"	(Rs.)	52629.34	60.90	54265.95	61.46	61923.39	62.67	57687.91	61.71
17	Rent paid for Leased in land	(Rs.)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
18	COST "A₂"	(Rs.)	52629.34	60.90	54265.95	61.46	61923.39	62.67	57687.91	61.71
19	Fixed capital	(Rs.)	13098.98	15.16	17217.17	19.50	16098.15	16.29	15471.44	16.55
20	Interest on Fixed Capital @ 10%	(Rs.)	1309.90	1.52	1721.72	1.95	1609.82	1.63	1547.14	1.66
21	COST "B₁"	(Rs.)	53939.24	62.42	55987.67	63.41	63533.20	64.30	59235.05	63.37
22	Rental Value of Land	(Rs.)	21350.78	24.71	20274.37	22.96	21316.25	21.57	21714.76	23.23
23	COST "B₂"	(Rs.)	75290.01	87.12	76262.03	86.37	84849.45	85.87	80949.81	86.60
24	Family Human Labour	Male	1967.68	2.28	2376.00	2.69	2784.60	2.82	2404.37	2.57
		Female	1305.00	1.51	1628.24	1.84	2193.57	2.22	1627.45	1.74
		Total	3272.68	3.79	4004.24	4.54	4978.17	5.04	4031.82	4.31
25	Cost " C₁ "	(Rs.)	57211.92	66.20	59991.91	67.95	68511.37	69.34	63266.87	67.68
26	Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	78562.69	90.91	80266.28	90.91	89827.62	90.91	84981.63	90.91
27	10% Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	7856.27		8026.63		8982.76		8498.16	
28	Cost " C₃ "	(Rs.)	86418.96	100.00	88292.91	100.00	98810.38	100.00	93479.79	100.00
29	Yield per hectare	(Rs)	128530.78		122176.07		128425.37		130801.03	
30	Per quintal cost of Production	(Rs.)	4844.11		5334.92		5665.73		5222.33	

Table No: 3 Cost of cultivation of cotton of non-beneficiary farmers.

(RS./ha)

Particulars			Small		Medium		Large		Overall	
Sr. No.	Item	Unit	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C3'
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	6389.42	8.66	6234.04	8.15	4936.12	5.88	5967.85	7.34
		Female	12976.45	17.60	14316.18	18.71	15998.26	19.06	14231.50	17.51
		Total	19365.87	26.26	20550.22	26.86	20934.38	24.94	20199.35	24.86
2	Bullock Labour	Hired	3008.58	3.39	3102.31	3.01	5227.34	5.18	5227.34	5.39
		Owned	1220.12	1.37	550.69	0.53	1612.42	1.60	1612.42	1.66
		Total	4228.70	4.76	3652.99	3.55	6839.76	6.78	6839.76	7.05
3	Machine charges	Hired	2329.71	2.87	1833.66	2.18	2886.29	3.13	2284.03	2.56
4	Seed	Kg/ha	2141.40	2.64	2201.60	2.62	2184.40	2.37	2175.80	2.43
5	Manures	Tonnes	2022.21	2.49	1169.44	1.39	3900.00	4.22	2275.00	2.55
6	Fertilizers	N kg/ha	366.42	0.45	548.98	0.65	392.50	0.43	583.02	0.65
		P kg/ha	1271.53	1.57	1361.12	1.62	1181.03	1.28	1294.60	1.45
		K kg/ha	562.00	0.69	601.60	0.71	522.00	0.57	572.20	0.64
		Total	2199.95	2.71	2511.70	2.98	2095.53	2.27	2449.82	2.74
7	Irrigation charges	(Rs.)	894.53	1.10	845.30	1.00	852.48	0.92	865.55	0.97
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)	1207.03	1.49	1013.69	1.20	1268.80	1.37	1149.97	1.29
9	Plant Protection	(Rs.)	4160.19	5.13	4036.32	4.80	4193.56	4.54	4122.08	4.61
10	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)	853.26	1.05	605.82	0.72	918.20	0.99	776.79	0.87
11	Harvesting	(Rs.)	9704.00	11.96	11376.00	13.51	10976.00	11.89	10480.00	11.72
12	Working Capital	(Rs.)	49106.85	60.54	49796.74	59.16	57049.39	61.79	53618.14	59.98
13	Interest on working Capital	(Rs.)	3075.14	3.79	3112.68	3.70	3548.87	3.84	3213.73	3.60
14	Depreciation	(Rs.)	850.91	1.05	850.91	1.01	474.64	0.51	670.79	0.75
15	Land Revenue	(Rs.)	89.42	0.11	94.20	0.11	97.02	0.11	101.99	0.11

16	COST "A₁"	(Rs.)	53122.32	65.49	53854.53	63.98	61169.92	66.25	57604.65	64.44
17	Rent paid for Leased in land	(Rs.)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
18	COST "A₂"	(Rs.)	53122.32	65.49	53854.53	63.98	61169.92	66.25	57604.65	64.44
19	Fixed capital	(Rs.)	16180.73	19.95	16180.73	19.22	16180.73	17.53	15570.84	17.42
20	Interest on Fixed Capital @ 10%	(Rs.)	1618.07	1.99	1618.07	1.92	1618.07	1.75	1557.08	1.74
21	COST "B₁"	(Rs.)	54740.39	67.48	55472.60	65.90	62787.99	68.00	59161.74	66.19
22	Rental Value of Land	(Rs.)	14707.66	18.13	17079.67	20.29	16716.52	18.11	16060.44	17.97
23	COST "B₂"	(Rs.)	69448.06	85.61	72552.27	86.19	79504.51	86.11	75222.18	84.15
24	Family Human Labour	Male	2799.28	3.45	2714.78	3.23	2063.46	2.23	2584.55	2.89
		Female	1498.44	1.85	1255.16	1.49	2367.28	2.56	3454.74	3.86
		Total	4297.72	5.30	3969.94	4.72	4430.74	4.80	6039.29	6.76
25	Cost " C₁ "	(Rs.)	59038.12	72.78	59442.54	70.62	67218.74	72.80	65201.02	72.94
26	Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	73745.78	90.91	76522.21	90.91	83935.26	90.91	81261.46	90.91
27	10% Cost " C₂ "	(Rs.)	7374.58		7652.22		8393.53		8126.15	
28	Cost " C₃ "	(Rs.)	81120.36	100.00	84174.44	100.00	92328.78	100.00	89387.61	100.00
29	Yield per hectare	(Rs)	88782.50		103043.24		100881.24		96974.58	
30	Per quintal cost of Production	(Rs.)	6687.58		5919.44		6729.50		6823.48	

Table No: 4 Per hectare cost and returns from cotton beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Reach (Beneficiary)				Size of holding (non-beneficiary)			
		Head Reach	Mid Reach	Tail Reach	Overall	Small	Medium	Large	Overall
1	Main Produce (Qtls)	17.84	16.55	17.44	17.90	12.13	14.22	13.72	13.10
	Price (Rs.)	7204.64	7382.24	7363.84	7307.32	7319.25	7246.36	7352.86	7402.64
	Value of Main Produce (Rs.)	128530.78	122176.07	128425.37	130801.03	88782.50	103043.24	100881.24	96974.58
2	Total Cost				Total Cost				
	Cost A1	52629.34	54265.95	61923.39	57687.91	53122.32	53854.53	61169.92	57604.65
	Cost A2	52629.34	54265.95	61923.39	57687.91	53122.32	53854.53	61169.92	57604.65
	Cost B1	53939.24	55987.67	63533.20	59235.05	54740.39	55472.60	62787.99	59161.74
	Cost B2	75290.01	76262.03	84849.45	80949.81	69448.06	72552.27	79504.51	75222.18
	Cost C1	57211.92	59991.91	68511.37	63266.87	59038.12	59442.54	67218.74	65201.02
	Cost C2	78562.69	80266.28	89827.62	84981.63	73745.78	76522.21	83935.26	81261.46
Cost C3	86418.96	88292.91	98810.38	93479.79	81120.36	84174.44	92328.78	89387.61	
3	Net Return Over				Net Return Over				
	Cost A1	75901.44	67910.12	66501.98	73113.12	35660.18	49188.71	39711.32	39369.93
	Cost A2	75901.44	67910.12	66501.98	73113.12	35660.18	49188.71	39711.32	39369.93
	Cost B1	74591.54	66188.40	64892.17	71565.98	34042.11	47570.64	38093.25	37812.84
	Cost B2	53240.77	45914.04	43575.92	49851.22	19334.44	30490.97	21376.73	21752.40
	Cost C1	71318.86	62184.16	59914.00	67534.16	29744.38	43600.70	33662.50	31773.56
	Cost C2	49968.09	41909.79	38597.75	45819.40	15036.72	26521.03	16945.98	15713.12
Cost C3	42111.82	33883.16	29614.99	37321.24	7662.14	18868.80	8552.46	7586.97	
4	Input- output Ratio				Input- output Ratio				
	Cost A1	2.44	2.25	2.07	2.27	1.67	1.91	1.65	1.68
	Cost A2	2.44	2.25	2.07	2.27	1.67	1.91	1.65	1.68
	Cost B1	2.38	2.18	2.02	2.21	1.62	1.86	1.61	1.64
	Cost B2	1.71	1.60	1.51	1.62	1.28	1.42	1.27	1.29
	Cost C1	2.25	2.04	1.87	2.07	1.50	1.73	1.50	1.49
	Cost C2	1.64	1.52	1.43	1.54	1.20	1.35	1.20	1.19
Cost C3	1.49	1.38	1.30	1.40	1.09	1.22	1.09	1.08	